

Legal Research Methodology: Citation Of Legal Authorities Based On OSCOLA And NALT Style Of Referencing

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ABSTRACT

Legal citation is a standard set of guidelines that allows a legal writer to refer to legal authorities and sources so that the reader can locate those sources. There are many styles of referencing for legal writing. However, the most widely used styles of referencing for legal writers in Nigeria are OSCOLA and NALT Style of Referencing. The aim of this paper is to illustrate the citation of legal authorities using OSCOLA and NALT Guide. It identifies the sources of legal authorities and explains the rules for the citation of cases, statutes, articles in journals, internet sources and unpublished materials. It also examines the special rules that apply to the citation of books and articles by multiple authors. It found that the NALT Guide is an adaptation of OSCOLA to local circumstances. However, there are many inconsistencies in the NALT Guide especially in the citation of books and articles in journals. Therefore, the paper suggests that where there are inconsistencies and ambiguities in the NALT Guide, OSCOLA should be used to resolve them.

Keywords: Doctrinal Statement; Legal Citation; Primary Sources; Secondary Sources

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Legal citation is a standard set of guidelines that allows a legal writer to refer to legal authorities and sources to enable the reader to locate those sources. To enable the reader to locate the sources easily, legal writers must cite legal authorities such as cases, statutes and other sources accurately and consistently. Thus, the two essential principles of legal citation are accuracy and consistency.¹

Referencing or citing legal authorities and other sources is an important part of academic legal writing as well as scholarly writing. It is the backbone of legal documentation and performs the following functions:

- (a) To acknowledge the ideas or works of others if you use them in your work;
- (b) To demonstrate the body of knowledge upon which your research is based;
- (c) To enable all those who read your work to locate your sources easily.²

The aim of this paper is to illustrate the citation of legal authorities based on OSCOLA³ and NALT Uniform Format and Citation Guide⁴ in academic and scholarly writing. It provides answers to three main questions: When to cite? What to cite? And how to cite? It explains the rules for the citation of cases, statutes, articles in journals, internet sources and unpublished materials in footnotes and bibliographies. It also examines the special rules that apply to the citation of scholarly papers by multiple authors.

The paper found that the NALT Guide is full of inconsistencies especially in the citation of books and articles in journals. Since the NALT Guide is said to be an adaptation of OSCOLA to local

¹ *Oketaolegun v State* [2015] All FWLR (Pt. 797) 677, 690 A-C (Galadima JSC); Becky Batagol and Melissa Castan, 'Citations, Sources and References' [2012] 37(1) Alt LJ 50, 50; RB Lamptey and H Atta-Obeng, 'Challenges with Reference Citations among Postgraduate Students in Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana' [2012] 32(3) *Journal of Science and Technology* 69, 79.

² MJ Baker, 'Writing the Literature Review' [2000] 1 *The Marketing Review* 219, 226;

³ University of Oxford, *Oxford Standard for the Citation of Legal Authorities* (4th edn, Hart Publishing 2012) ('OSCOLA').

⁴ Nigerian Association of Law Teachers, *NALT Uniform Format and Citation Guide for Legal Research Writing in Nigeria* (NALT 2021) ('NALT Guide').

circumstances, the paper suggests that legal writers in Nigeria should first study and master OSCOLA and use it alongside the NALT Guide. It also suggests that where there are inconsistencies in the NALT Guide, OSCOLA should be used to resolve them.

2.0 When to Cite?

As a legal writer, you should cite references in support of doctrinal statements. **Doctrinal statements** are statements of law or legal principles in cases and statutes. Thus, every statement of law must be followed by a citation to the source.⁵ If you are citing a statute or other primary source, you should also cite at least one case in support of your interpretation of the statute.⁶

You should also cite references for quotations as well as statements of facts and thoughts, opinions or ideas of other authors, even though you are not using direct quotations.⁷ Even if you have paraphrased the thoughts, opinions or ideas of other authors, you must still cite the source.⁸ You should always go to the original source when you are making reference to a statement of facts or quotation.⁹

3.0 What to Cite?

There are two main sources of authority for legal writing. These are primary sources and secondary sources. There should be a balance between primary and secondary sources in your work.¹⁰ **Primary sources** are cases, statutes and treaties.¹¹ **Secondary sources** are used to explain, interpret and analyze the primary sources. They include textbooks, articles in journal and unpublished works such as students' projects, theses and dissertations.¹²

There are materials printed solely on the internet. These are also secondary sources. But there are other materials that are merely hosted on the internet such as statutes and cases. Nevertheless, these are primary sources.

Primary sources must be cited in support of doctrinal statements.¹³ Secondary sources are only supplementary to primary sources in support of doctrinal statements. It is, therefore, wrong to cite secondary sources solely in support of doctrinal statement, but they can be cited to supplement or complement a primary source.¹⁴

4.0 How to Cite?

There are many referencing styles for legal writers. However, the most widely used citation formats for legal writers in Nigeria are OSCOLA and NALT style of referencing. The NALT style of referencing is stated to be an adaptation of OSCOLA to local circumstances.¹⁵ The following citation guide is based on OSCOLA and NALT Style of Referencing.

4.1 Primary sources:

4.1.1 Cases:

⁵ Nina E Kallen, 'How to Win a Summary Judgement' <<https://www.kallenlawyer.com>> accessed 29 March 2026.

⁶ Emily Watson, 'How to Quote a Quote: Quotation Mark Rules and Examples' <<https://www.essaydone.ai>> accessed 29 March 2026.

⁷ FAMU Libraries, 'When Do I Cite?' <<https://library.famu.edu>> accessed 29 March 2026.

⁸ Emily Watson, 'How to Quote a Quote: Quotation Mark Rules and Examples' <<https://www.essaydone.ai>> accessed 29 March 2026.

⁹ Gerald Lebovits, 'You Can Quote Me: Quoting in Legal Writing – Part I' [2004] 76(4) *New York State Bar Association Journal* 59.

¹⁰ TL Sajeevanie, 'Literature Review and Academic Research' [2021] 9(1) *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts* 2713, 2716; AS Denney and R Tewksbury, 'How to Write a Literature Review' [2012] *Journal of Criminal Justice Education* 1, 10.

¹¹ CM Bast and M Hawkins, *Foundations of Legal Research and Writing* (4th edn, Cengage Learning 2010) 131.

¹² Richard K Neumann, Jr. and Kristen K Tiscione, *Legal Reasoning and Legal Writing* (7th edn, Wolters Kluwer 2013) para. 8.3.1.

¹³ Emily Watson, 'How to Quote a Quote: Quotation Mark Rules and Examples' <<https://www.essaydone.ai>> accessed 29 March 2026.

¹⁴ Priya Verma, 'Doctrinal Legal Research in a Globalizing World' 6-9 <www.academia.edu> accessed 20 May 2023; Ian Dobinson and Francis Johns, 'Qualitative Legal Research' in Mike McConville and Wing Hong Chui (eds), *Research Methods for Law* (Edinburg University Press 2007) 23.

¹⁵ NALT Guide (n 4) 105.

The components of a typical case citation consist of the name of the case in italics, the year the case was reported in square brackets or round brackets which must be used consistently throughout the work, followed by the volume, the report abbreviation, the part in round brackets, if applicable, and the first page and, where necessary, the court in round brackets. The case name should be in italics with an unpunctuated italic *v* to separate the names of adverse parties.¹⁶ Use Arabic numerals for volume, part and page numbers. There are no full stops in the report abbreviation, for example, ‘AC’ rather than ‘A.C.’ and ‘SC’ rather than ‘S.C.’¹⁷ For example:

Page v Smith [1996] AC 155 (HL)
Olaniyan v University of Lagos [1985] 2 NWLR (Pt 9) 599 (SC)

When pinpointing or making a reference to a particular page number, give the page number on which the reference can be found. Multiple page number pinpoints should be separated by commas.¹⁸ For example:

Page v Smith (1996) AC 155 (HL) 188, 222
Olaniyan v University of Lagos [1985] 1 NWLR (Pt 9) 599, 642, 661

4.1.2 Statutes:

Cite an Act by its short title and year, using capitals for the major words and without a comma before the year.¹⁹ For example:

Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1985
Shipping and Trading Interests (Protection) Act 1995

If several jurisdictions are discussed in a work, it may be necessary to add the jurisdiction in brackets at the end of the citation.²⁰ For example:

Shipping and Trading Interests (Protection) Act 1995 (UK)
Employee Compensation Act 2010 (Nigeria)

If specifying a section, subsection or paragraph, use only the abbreviation for the section. You should have a comma after the year, and a space but no full stop between the abbreviation and the initial number, letter or opening bracket. For example, paragraph (b) of subsection (1) of section 15 of the Human Rights Act 1998 is cited as follows:²¹

Human Rights Act 1998, s 15(1)(b)
Trade Disputes Act 2004, s 42(1)(a)

4.2 Secondary Sources:

4.2.1 Books:

Cite the author’s name exactly as it appears in the publication, followed by a comma, and then the title of the book in italics. The publication information (that is, the name of the publisher and the year of publication should be enclosed in round brackets). Omit post nominals such as Prof, Dr, JP, QC and Esq. The citation should be in this form: author, *title in italics* (publisher/year).²² For example:

Timothy Endicott, *Administrative Law* (Oxford University Press 2009)

Where a book has a title and a subtitle, the title should be separated from the subtitle with a colon.²³ For example:

P Oluyede, *Administrative Law: Cases and Materials* (Sweet & Maxell 2008)

Where there are two authors, insert ‘and’ between their names. For example:

OVC Okene and GG Otuturu, *Nigerian Company Law and Practice* (Zubic Infinity Concepts 2021)

¹⁶ University of Salford, ‘Guide to Using OSCOLA for Legal Referencing’ 3 <www.library.salford.ac.uk> accessed 20 November 2018.

¹⁷ Ibid 4.

¹⁸ OSCOLS (n 3) 19.

¹⁹ Ibid 23.

²⁰ Ibid 24.

²¹ Ibid 24.

²² Ibid 33.

²³ Ibid 34.

Where there are up to three authors, insert 'and' between their names as in the following example.²⁴

D Chambers, G Davies and G Monti, *European Union Law: Text and Materials* (2nd edn, CUP 2010)

Where there are more than three authors, give the details of the first author followed by 'and others'.²⁵ as in the following example:²⁶

D Chambers and others, *European Union Law: Text and Materials* (CUP 2005)

If no individual author is identified, but an organization or institution claims editorial responsibility for the work, then cite it as the author. Italicize the titles of books and similar publications. If there is no author, begin the citation with the title of the work. Treat editors' names in the same way as authors' names.²⁷ Cite all publications with ISBN as if they were books, whether read online or in hard copy.²⁸ For example:

Rivers State University of Science and Technology, *Guidelines for Post Graduate Dissertation* (RSUST 2012)

If you are citing an edition other than the first edition, indicate it by adding '2nd edn' (for second edition) or 'rev edn' (for revised edition). Additional information should be separated with a comma before the publisher and year of publication in round brackets. The citation should be in this form: author, *title of book in italics* (edition, publisher and year).²⁹ For example:

OVC Okene, *Labour Law in Nigeria: The Law of Work* (3rd edn, Claxton and Derrick Ltd 2001)

If a book consists of more than one volume, the volume follows the publication details, unless the publication details of the volume vary, in which case it precedes them, and is separated from the title by a comma. Pinpoint paragraphs rather than pages if the paragraphs are numbered. For example:³⁰

Christian von Bar, *The Common Law of Torts*, vol. 2 (CH Beck 2000) para 76

In footnotes, write the author's forenames or initials before surname, for example, WH Dutton. In bibliographies, write the author's surname followed by initials without punctuation between them, for example, Dutton WH. A comma is placed after the final initial.³¹ Citation in in bibliography does not carry page number for books except for chapter contributions and articles in journals which must end with the first page.³²

Citation in a footnote:

WH Dutton and PW Jeffrey (eds), *World Wide Research: Reshaping the Sciences and Humanities in the Century of Information* (MIT Press 2010) 210.

Citation in a bibliography:

Dutton WH and Jeffrey PW (eds), *World Wide Research: Reshaping the Sciences and Humanities in the Century of Information* (MIT Press 2010)

4.2.2 Chapter Contributions in Books:

To identify a particular chapter in a book edited by one or more people, cite the author and title of the contribution in a similar format used when citing an article, followed by the editor's name with 'ed' (for one editor) or 'eds' (for more than one editor) in brackets, the title of the book in italics, and the publication information in round brackets.³³

²⁴ OSCOLA (n 16) 12.

²⁵ OSCOLA (n 3) 33.

²⁶ OSCOLA (n 16) 12.

²⁷ OSCOLA (n 3) 33.

²⁸ Ibid 34.

²⁹ Ibid 34.

³⁰ Ibid 34.

³¹ Ibid 33.

³² Ibid 37.

³³ Ibid 35.

The citation of a chapter contribution in an edited book should be in this form: author, 'title of chapter in single quotation marks' in (ed), *title of book in italics* (additional information, publisher/year). For example:

Justine Pila, 'The Value of Authorship in the Digital Environment' in William H Dutton and Paul W Jeffrey (eds), *World Wide Research: Reshaping the Sciences and Humanities in the Century of Information* (MIT Press 2010) 210.

4.2.3 Articles in Journals:

For articles in a hard copy journal, give the author's name first, followed by a comma, and then give the title of the article within single quotation marks. The title of the article should be in sentence caps. The year of publication should be in square brackets, followed by the volume number, the issue number in round brackets immediately after the volume number, and the first page of the article.³⁴

The citation of an article in journal should be in this form: author, 'title of the paper in single brackets' [year of publication in square brackets] volume (issue in round brackets) *journal name in italics* followed by the page number. Put a comma after the first page of the article if there is a pinpoint.³⁵ For example:

JG Abraham, 'The Common Law and the Nigerian Constitution' [2001] 17(2) *Modern Practice Journal of Finance and Investment Law* 42
GG Otuturu, 'Legal Research Methodology: A Practical Approach to Research Report Writing' [2025] 10(1) *Journal of Law and Global Policy* 37, 45

For articles in online journal, which has been published electronically, provide publication details as you would for articles in hard copy journals but bear in mind that some of the elements available in printed form may not be available. The citation should be followed by the web address in angle brackets (< >) and the date you accessed the article. Pinpoint follows the citation and comes before the web address.³⁶ The format for online articles should be: author, 'title of publication' [year] volume (issue) *journal name or abbreviation* pinpoint <web address> date accessed. For example:

Graham Greenleaf, 'The Global Development of Free Access to Legal Information' [2010] 1(1) *EJLT* 210 <<http://ejlt.org/article/view/17>> accessed 27 July 2010.

4.2.4 Encyclopaedia:

Cite an encyclopaedia much as you would cite a book, but exclude the author or editor and publisher and include the edition and year of issue or reissue. Pinpoints to volumes and paragraphs come after the publication information. When an encyclopaedia credits an author for a segment, give both the author and the segment title at the beginning of the citation. If citing an online encyclopaedia, give the web address and date of access.³⁷ For example:

Halsbury's Laws of England (5th edn, 2010) vol. 57, para 53
Leslie Green, 'Legal Positivism', *The Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy* (2nd edn, 2009) <<http://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2009/entries/legal-positivism>> accessed 20 November 2019

4.2.5 Case Notes:

Cite case notes with title as if they were journal articles. Where there is no title, use the name of the case in italics instead and add note in round brackets at the end of the citation.³⁸ For example:

³⁴ Ibid 37.

³⁵ Ibid 37.

³⁶ Ibid 38.

³⁷ Ibid 36.

³⁸ Ibid 37.

GG Otuturu, 'Categories of Contract of Employment: A Note on Union Bank of Nigeria Plc v Ogboh' [2005] 9 (1-2) *Modern Practice Journal of Finance and Investment Law* 201
Andrew Ashworth, 'FRN v Adams Oshiomhole' [2008] *Nigerian Bar Review* 441 (note).

4.2.6 Conference Papers:

When citing a conference paper, give the author, the title in single quotation marks, the title of the conference, location and date of conference in round brackets. If the conference paper has been published, cite the published version instead. Papers that are available online should include a web address and date of access.³⁹ For example:

Ben McFarlane and Donald Nolan, 'Remembering Reliance: The Future Development of Promissory and Proprietary Estoppel in English Law' (Obligations III Conference, Brisbane, July 2006)

4.2.7 Theses and Dissertations:

When citing an unpublished thesis or dissertation, give the name of the author, the title of the thesis or dissertation and, in brackets, give the type of thesis, university and year of completion. Pinpoint comes after the brackets.⁴⁰ For example:

Javan Herberg, 'Injunctive Relief for Wrongful Termination of Employment' (PhD thesis, University of Oxford 1989) 190

4.2.8 Newspaper Articles:

When citing newspaper article, give the author, the title, the name of the newspaper in italics and then in brackets the city of publication and the date. There are different styles of writing the date. Follow the style adopted in your country. If known, give the page number on which the article was published, after the brackets.⁴¹ For example:

Jane Croft, 'Supreme Court Warns on Quality' *Financial Times* (London, 1 July 2010) 3

4.2.9 Personal Communication:

When citing a personal communication, give the author and recipient of the communication, followed by the date in round brackets. For example:⁴²

Letter from Gordon Brown to Lady Ashton (20 November 2009)

4.2.10 Websites and Blogs:

If you access information from blogs, use the general format for citing electronic materials. If there is no author, begin the citation with the title in the usual way. If you cannot find a date of publication, provide the date you accessed it.⁴³ Follow the same format for citing information from websites.⁴⁴ For examples:

Blog:
Sarah Cole, 'Virtual Friend Fires Employee' (*Naked Law*, 1 May 2009)
<<http://www.nakedlaw.com/2009/05/index.html>> accessed 19 November 2009
Website:
Campaign for Freedom of Information, 'Whistle blowing'
<<http://www.cfoi.org.uk/whistle.html>> accessed 8 February 2011

³⁹ Ibid 41.

⁴⁰ Ibid 42.

⁴¹ Ibid 42.

⁴² Ibid 43.

⁴³ Ibid 42.

⁴⁴ OSCOLA (n 16) 15.

5.0 Summary of Findings

The NALT Guide is divided into four parts. Part 1 contains ‘Background Information to NALT Format’. Part 2 contains ‘NALT Format and the Structuring of Research Topics’ on students’ project writing with numerous examples on how to prepare and structure research topic into logical divisions.⁴⁵

Part 3 contains ‘NALT Citation Guidelines for Style of Referencing’⁴⁶ which is said to be an adaptation of OSCOLA to local circumstances⁴⁷ by ‘localizing the cases, the statutes and replacement of all foreign names with our local academic authors of books and journals.’⁴⁸ Part 4 contains ‘Format for Articles in Journals for Publication’ which is based on the manual of the Modern Language Association (MLA).⁴⁹

As the name suggests, the ‘NALT Uniform Format and Citation Guide’ declares that it is a uniform format and it retains ‘all the features, technicalities and the principles in OSCOLA style of referencing.’⁵⁰ However, there are many inconsistencies in the NALT Guide especially in the citation of textbooks and articles in journals.

On the citation of textbooks, the NALT Guide gives the following inconsistent citation formats:

Muhammed Tawfiq Ladan, *Sustainable Development Goals: Climate Change and Extractive Resource Management in Africa* (Ahmadu Bello University Press Limited Zaria 2017).⁵¹

David Jangkam, ‘The Value of Authorship in the Digital Environment’ in Clement Francis Kwale and Karen Shaakaa (eds), *World Wide Research: Reshaping the Sciences and Humanities in the Century of Information* (MIT, 2010) 62.⁵²

Bethel U Ihugba, ‘Resolution of Farmland Disputes and Agricultural Development: An Examination of the Judicial System in Settlement of Farmland Disputes’ in Rhuks T. Ako and Damilola S. Olawuyi (eds) *Food and Agriculture Law: Readings on Sustainable Agriculture and the Law in Nigeria* (Afe Babalola University Press, Ado Ekiti, 2015) 48-64.⁵³

Both OSCOLA and NALT Guide use as little punctuation as possible.⁵⁴ For example, abbreviations and initials in author’s names do not take full stops.⁵⁵ The place of publication is not required.⁵⁶ This clearly shows the inconsistencies in the NALT Guide. In the first example, the publication information contains the place of publication. In the second example, there is comma separating the publisher from the year of publication. In the third example, there are full stops in the authors’ initials. It is worse with the citation of articles in journals. Different citation formats are used in the citation of articles in journals in both the NALT Guide and the NALT Manual. For example:

EI Alemika, ‘Criminal Justice System and Respect for Human Rights: Problems and Imperative for Reform’. *Human Rights Review: An International Human Rights Journal* [2011] (12)(2) 25.⁵⁷

TO Oyelami, ‘A Comparative Appraisal of the Realization of Some Aspects of

⁴⁵ NALT Guide (n 4) 7.

⁴⁶ Part III of the NALT Guide is the same Part II online titled ‘NALT Uniform Format and Citation Guide - Style of Referencing’ <<https://www.nalt-style-of-referencing>> accessed 20 November 2019.

⁴⁷ NALT Guide (n 4) 105.

⁴⁸ Ibid xxvii.

⁴⁹ Ibid 12.

⁵⁰ The current edition titled *NALT Manual on Uniform Format and Citation Guide on Legal Research* (4th edn, NALT 2025) (‘NALT Manual’) is practically the same with the NALT Guide except changes in page numbers.

⁵¹ NALT Guide (n 4) 70.

⁵² Ibid 70-71.

⁵³ Ibid 71.

⁵⁴ OSCOLA (n 3) 7

⁵⁵ Ibid 7.

⁵⁶ Ibid 34.

⁵⁷ NALT Guide (n 3) 75.

Human Rights under Generals Buhari and Babangida Administration'. *Current Jos Law Journal* [1999] 5(5) 153-172.⁵⁸
Madaki Adamu Izang, 'Case Review: Usman Kaza v. State (2008) 7 NWLR (Pt 1088) 125 (2014) 6 *Journal of Public Law and Constitutional Practice* 148-156.⁵⁹

In the first and second examples above, the name of the journal comes before the year of publication and the year of publication is put in round brackets. In the first example, the volume and issue of the journal are enclosed in round brackets. However, in the second example, only the volume is enclosed in round brackets, which is consistent with OSCOLA. In both examples, the year of publication of the journal is enclosed in square brackets, which is also consistent with OSCOLA.

In the third example, the year of publication of the law report and the journal is enclosed in round brackets instead of square brackets as in the first and second examples. However, unlike the first and second examples, the name of the journal comes after the year of publication and the volume of the journal, which is consistent with OSCOLA. The page (or page range) of the publication comes after the name of the journal, which is also consistent with OSCOLA.

6.0 Conclusion and Suggestions

The NALT Guide is an adaptation of OSCOLA to local circumstances in Nigeria. However, there are many inconsistencies in the NALT Guide as demonstrated above. It is, therefore, suggested that where there are inconsistencies or ambiguities in the NALT Guide, OSCOLA should be used to resolve them.

It is also suggested that legal writers in Nigeria should study and master OSCOLA and use it alongside the NALT Guide. In this way, obvious errors and inconsistencies in the NALT Guide could be corrected with OSCOLA.

⁵⁸ Ibid 76.

⁵⁹ Ibid 77.